

IMPLEMENTATION OF A MOLECULAR INTERPHASE MODEL WITHIN A MULTISCALE FRAMEWORK FOR POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of a novel methodology for modeling the interphase between carbon fiber and polymer matrix using atomistic scale simulations. The model is integrated within a multiscale framework for the analysis of polymer matrix composites. The interphase region that exists between carbon fiber and polymer matrix plays an important role in damage initiation and it is critical for modeling damage propagation across length scales. The developed interphase model in this work consists of multiple pseudo-damaged graphene layers, and is capable of capturing the physical entanglement between the polymer matrix and the carbon fiber through the use of molecular dynamics simulations. The pseudo-damage model simulates voids in the graphene layer by removing carbon atoms, while multiple pseudo-damaged graphene layers represent the amorphous structure of the carbon fiber surface. In order to accurately model the chemical structure of the polymer, a numerical curing process is employed that captures the stochastic interactions between resin and hardener molecules for crosslinking (carbon-nitrogen covalent bond generation). The molecular dynamics model also enables extraction of the material properties of the interphase at the nanoscale which is then integrated within a high fidelity generalized method of cells micromechanics theory. A modified Bodner-Partom viscoplastic theory is applied to the polymer matrix subcells. Additionally, progressive damage and failure theories are used at different scales in the modeling framework to accurately capture scale-dependent failure of the composite material. Comparative studies are performed by applying different interphase properties that are obtained from the literature to the interphase subcells. The results indicate that the responses for each type of interphase model are similar, but the transverse tensile strength, obtained using the MD simulated interphase properties, is approximately 7% lower than the other interphase types and also has a maximum difference of 10% in failure strain.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the high complexity of the polymer matrix composite (PMC) structure and an increased interest in designing these materials for aerospace applications, accurate multiscale modeling of PMCs is needed in order to study their scale-dependent damage and failure characteristics. Several studies have employed multiscale modeling tools for material damage and behavior. Voyiadjis et al. [1] developed a multiscale model including damage and plasticity variables at the meso- and macroscale. Yu and Fish [2] used asymptotic homogenization for the spatial and temporal domains to model viscoelastic behavior of composites. Macroscopic failure of composite structures was modeled using a multiscale progressive failure technique by Laurin et al. [3]. Liu [4] and Liu et al. [5] used a multiscale modeling framework based on the generalized method of cells to study the rate dependent behavior and failure of composites with complex architectures. Most of these studies examine damage and failure to determine the effect on the material response at different scales, but they assume that perfect bonding conditions exist between the fiber and the polymer matrix. Whereas the interaction at the interphase between the fiber and polymer matrix is not perfect; therefore, the defects that exist in this region can cause damage initiation and propagation.

However, the determination of material properties and failure criteria for the interphase region, given its small size and intricacies, is a challenging task. McCullough et al. [6] outlined many

micromechanical models that include the interphase in order to predict the macroscopic behavior of composite materials reinforced with carbon/glass fibers. Several finite element analysis (FEA) methods have been developed to account for the interphase by defining cohesive elements to this region. Asp et al. [7] assumed symmetrical and periodic conditions in order to use FEA to model a quarter of the fiber in polymer matrix and studied the effects of interphase thickness on the resulting properties. Souza et al. [8] developed a multiscale model incorporating viscoelasticity in a micromechanical model and a cohesive zone model to determine the effect of damage under impact loading. Hettich et al. [9] created a variational model, which decomposed the displacement field in order to model cracks at different length scales. FEA has also been used to model representative volume elements (RVEs) consisting of multiple fibers and the interphase was added by applying bilinear cohesive laws [10, 11]. Similar types of cohesive laws have been applied to the generalized method of cell theory [12, 13] where the subcell interfacial boundary condition integrates the cohesive law within the mathematical theory. Although a large number of studies have applied interfacial laws to account for the fiber/matrix interaction, only a few attempt to characterize or simulate the physical molecular structure of this region due to its small scale and difficulty in performing experimentation at this scale.

To address the physical and experimental challenges presented by the interphase, some studies utilize atomistic simulation methods, such as *ab-initio*, density functional theory and molecular dynamics (MD) simulation method which attempt to capture the interatomic/intermolecular interaction at the material level. However, there have only been a limited number of studies that consider the interphase between carbon fiber and polymer matrix at the molecular level. Currently, most interphase models are developed for carbon nanotube (CNT) reinforced nanocomposites or graphene embedded nanocomposites [14, 15]. MD simulations have been performed to analyze the mechanical properties of these CNT reinforced polymer [14] and to simulate multilayer, graphene embedded polymer using van der Waals interactions [15]. Zhang et al. [11] have implemented an approach that consists of multiple graphene layers and a molecular polymer model to estimate the mechanical properties of PMCs. However, Zhang's interphase model was solely formulated from the Lennard-Jones potential and does not account for mechanical bonding. This assumption, that the Lennard-Jones potential is the only driving interaction in the interphase, may improve the computational efficiency, but the accuracy of the estimated material properties is significantly compromised because the model does not adequately capture the physical entanglement between the amorphous carbon fiber and the polymer matrix at the molecular level. The current study accounts for mechanical bonding through an MD interphase model, which applies a pseudo-damaging method to several graphene layers enabling physical entanglement of the polymer with the carbon fiber surface.

The focus of this study is to develop a reliable molecular model of the fiber/matrix interphase and to analyze the effect the molecular interphase model has on the composite response at the larger length scales. The aforementioned pseudo-damaging method simulates the molecular structure of the interphase by removing carbon atoms from several pristine graphene layers. The removal of the carbon atoms generates voids in the graphene layers, thereby representing the amorphous structure of the carbon fiber. A simulated curing process, previously implemented by the coauthors [16], is applied to the thermoset polymer constituent (resin/hardener) in MD simulations, allowing polymer chain generation through this void, which then creates a physical interaction between the fiber and polymer matrix. Loading conditions are applied to this model and the properties are integrated with micromechanical theories. The high fidelity generalized method of cells (HFGMC) [17, 19] micromechanical theory is utilized in this study due to its higher order displacement field which enables complex relations between subcells. In addition to the MD simulated properties, interphasial properties are extracted from several sources [7, 10, 11] and incorporated into the HFGMC theory for comparison. Microfailure and microdamage theories, previously used by the authors in a sectional micromechanics approach [19, 20], are applied to the current model. The current multiscale model is able to investigate the effects of the interphase on the behavior and failure of the composite material by explicitly modeling the interphase through MD simulations. The main contribution of this work is the development of a multiscale modeling framework that simulates the physical molecular interactions of the interphase and is capable of capturing carbon fiber defects in the interphasial region.

2 NANOSCALE MODELING METHODS

MD simulations are used in this work to virtually characterize the material properties of the interphase region in PMCs. As previously stated, the interphase is a critical, complex region of the PMC material and accurate models are needed to reliably determine progressive damage and failure of the material. The interphase model first considers the atomistic content and structure of each distinct phase. The epoxy curing process, involving covalent bond generation between resin and hardener, simulates the thermoset polymer matrix by using a cut-off distance based bond generation approach [16]. Finally, the processes of both developing a molecular model of carbon fiber and integrating the thermoset polymer matrix and carbon fiber molecular model are presented.

2.1 Polymer Matrix

A significant amount of work has been reported on experimental methods for the characterization and fabrication of thermoset polymer; however, experimentally characterizing the material properties requires a large amount of time and expense. In the pursuit of developing a numerical approach as an alternative, the MD simulation approach is introduced. A majority of the MD simulated polymer research to date has been based on the epoxy resin Di-Glycidyl Ether of Bisphenol F (DGEBF) with different hardeners such as Diethyltoluenediamine (DETDA) [21], Triethylene tetramine (TETA) [22], and Isophorane Diamine (IPD) [23]. In this paper, an MD simulation approach is used to investigate the interphase model using DGEBF and Di-Ethylene Tri-Amine (DETA). Previously, the authors reported a detailed procedure to simulate the epoxy curing process using a cut-off distance based covalent bond generation technique [16]. This same methodology is used for the epoxy resin and hardener in the current interphase model. The number of molecules are determined by a weight ratio of 100:27 (DGEBF:DETA), determined experimentally. Table 1 contains the number of molecules in a polymer unit cell. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the 3D molecular structure of neat epoxy, which is combined with the molecular model of the carbon fiber surface to create the interphase model as discussed in the next section.

Figure 1: Schematic of neat epoxy unit cell.

	Weight	Formula	# of molecules
DGEBF	313 g/mol	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	260
DETA	103 g/mol	C ₄ H ₁₃ N ₃	220

Table 1: Components of neat epoxy (100:27).

In order to perform MD simulations, an appropriate force field for the epoxy system needs to be assigned. Several force fields have been developed specifically for epoxy-based systems. Lin et al. [24] used Assisted Model Building with Energy Refinement (AMBER) for an epoxy network consisting of DGEBA and trimethylene glycol di-p-aminobenzoate (TMAB). Li et al. [25] used the Dreiding force field for DGEBA and 33DDS atomistic simulation. Bandyopadhyay et al. [26] used Optimized Potential for Liquid Simulation (OPLS) for atomistic simulation of DGEBF and DETDA. Condensed-phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies (COMPASS) has been used for

polymer research, and many epoxy-based MD simulations have been conducted with various epoxy resins and hardeners [22, 27]. However, the best force field for epoxy-based systems has not been clearly defined and the ultimate determination of the force field should be confirmed through experimental validation. The Merck Molecular Force Field (MMFF) [28], which was developed for general organic research and pharmaceutical development, is used for the epoxy-based systems in this paper. In addition to the MMFF, all the simulations have been performed using the Large-scale Atomic Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) program developed by Sandia National Laboratory [29]. The glass transition temperature of polymers was previously examined using the MMFF and LAMMPS [16] and the error associated with these results was less than 2%.

2.2 Carbon Fiber Surface

Carbon fiber is often approximated as graphene or a CNT in order to reduce the number of atoms needed to fully represent the fiber. Graphene/CNTs possess crystalline structures whereas carbon fiber is amorphous, with chains of carbon atoms randomly folded and/or interlocked together [30]. In fact, the high stiffness, tensile strength, and temperature tolerance of carbon fiber, along with its low thermal expansion are attributed to its amorphous structure, as a result of which physical entanglement can be expected to occur between the carbon fiber surface and the surrounding polymer matrix. In this research work, a novel interphase model using pseudo-damaged multiple graphene layers is created to represent the carbon fiber surface. The pseudo-damaged graphene layers have carbon atoms removed from portions of the graphene layer to simulate voids in the structure. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the carbon surface model using multiple pseudo-damaged graphene layers. The interphase model is constructed by stacking a number of healthy graphene layers (N_h) with pseudo-damaged graphene layers (N_d). A simple $N_h:N_d:N_h$ (5:5:5) sequence of layers is used in this paper as shown in Figure 2. The number/sequence of layers and the shape of the damage are not varied, but parametric studies of these variables are planned for future work. For the graphene, an all-atom force field is implemented using OPLS to obtain the atomic and molecular interactions [31].

Figure 2: Schematic of pseudo-damaged graphene layer for carbon fiber surface representation; the number of healthy graphene layers (N_h) and the number of pseudo-damaged graphene layers (N_d).

2.3 Interphase Model and Tensile Simulation

The mixture and curing of epoxy resin and hardener with the pseudo-damaged graphene layers cause the epoxy network to form through the void, which physically entangles the carbon atom chains and epoxy network, as shown in Figure 3. Physically, the entanglement is caused by the generation of covalent bonding of the epoxy network. A large amount of energy is required to break these bonds when compared with the Lennard-Jones (non-bonded) potential energy. To investigate the material properties of the interphase, an RVE is constructed with the atomistic carbon fiber surface model and the randomly distributed molecules of epoxy resin and hardener. The initial dimensions of the unit cell are $100 \times 65 \times 50 \text{ \AA}^3$, consisting of the polymer (15,000 atoms) and the carbon fiber surface (15,840 atoms). Since this RVE is used as the interphase between carbon fiber and polymer, periodic boundary conditions are only applied along the y and z directions. Due to the multiple constituent phases in the x direction, periodic boundary conditions are not specified in this direction. Conjugate gradient energy minimization, using

the Nose–Hoover thermostat and barostat, is performed at 300K and 1atm for 100ps (1fs time step) prior to conducting the isobaric-isothermal (NPT) ensemble equilibration of the RVE. The system equilibration is achieved when the potential energy converges to a mean value with minimal variation. After the equilibration step, the molecules maintain minimum distances between themselves. Next, the MD simulator generates covalent bonds when the distances between the carbon atoms in the resin and the nitrogen atoms in the hardener are within a cutoff distance of 4Å, which is similar to the sum of van der Waals radii of C and N. After the numerical curing process, it was observed that a crosslinking degree (percentage of new C-N bond generation) of 52% was achieved. For a neat epoxy unit cell, the average crosslinking degree was 56%; hence, a 4% reduction occurs because the carbon atom chain inhibits the covalent bond generation.

Figure 3: a) Schematic of interphase molecular model using pseudo-damaged multiple graphene layers, b) diagram showing the periodic boundary conditions in the interphase model.

In order to stabilize the cured system, additional NPT ensemble simulations are performed until the total energy converges to a stable value. It is important to note that all the equilibration studies have been conducted with MMFF. However, MMFF (also known as the empirical force field) cannot capture inelastic behavior of the molecular system; therefore, it is not suitable for materials that exhibit this type of deformation. In order to overcome this critical issue, a bond-ordered force field, capable of capturing covalent bond breakage, has been introduced in this study. While there are several bond-ordered force fields in the literature to select from, the reactive force field developed by Singh et al. [32] is used in this study due to its strong compatibility with hydrocarbon amorphous materials. Figure 4 shows the loading conditions for the virtual tensile test where half of all the graphene layers are fixed in the x direction and a tensile force is applied to the polymer matrix molecules (resin and hardener) along the x axis. Using this virtual tensile test procedure, it is possible to obtain the transverse elastic modulus and transverse tensile strength of the molecular interphase, and these values are presented in section 4 of this paper.

Figure 4: Schematic of loading conditions for the virtual tensile test.

3 MICROMECHANICS MODELING THEORY

In this research work, the multiscale modeling framework uses the HFGMC micromechanics theory [17, 18] to model the microscale composite constituents. The modeling framework integrates the interphase properties obtained from the MD simulated nanoscale model by defining interphase subcells in the HFGMC geometry. The HFGMC theory enables shear coupling between the subcells through the application of a higher order displacement field (Equation 1). This coupling is essential for studying the effect of the interphase on the composite response and failure.

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_i^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} = & \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} x_j + W_{i(000)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \bar{y}_1^{(\alpha)} W_{i(100)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \bar{y}_2^{(\beta)} W_{i(010)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \bar{y}_3^{(\gamma)} W_{i(001)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \left(3\bar{y}_1^{(\alpha)2} - \frac{d_\alpha^2}{4} \right) W_{i(200)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \frac{1}{2} \left(3\bar{y}_2^{(\beta)2} - \frac{h_\beta^2}{4} \right) W_{i(020)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \frac{1}{2} \left(3\bar{y}_3^{(\gamma)2} - \frac{l_\gamma^2}{4} \right) W_{i(002)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)}
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, the $\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ tensor contains the average global strain components, $W_{i(000)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)}$ are the volume averaged displacements, the remaining $W_{i(lmn)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)}$ are higher order terms. The Greek symbols are indices that represent the directions of the subcell numbering and do not indicate summation, and the \bar{y} parameters represent coordinates within the particular subcell. The dimensions defined for each subcell are represented by the d_α , h_β , and l_γ parameters. The displacement field for each subcell is solved through the assignment of equilibrium, boundary conditions, and interfacial continuity conditions, and the solution procedure is detailed by Aboudi et al. [18]. A single fiber in polymer matrix is defined as the unit cell and the general subcell discretization of the unit cell is shown in Figure 5. The dimensions of the unit cell geometry are normalized before performing the analysis, and 400 subcells are defined in the unit cell. The interphase subcells are defined from a fiber/matrix unit cell by replacing the polymer subcells, immediately adjacent to the fiber subcells, with interphase subcells, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Discretization of unit cell into polymer (yellow), fiber (grey), and interphase (red) subcells.

The constitutive equations for the fiber subcells are represented by a transversely isotropic, linear elastic model (Equation 2) whereas the polymer subcells are represented by a modified Bodner-Partom viscoplastic state variable model [33]. Rate dependency and inelasticity are incorporated into the viscoplastic model, and the modification consists of an additional hydrostatic stress term of which the

details are presented by Goldberg et al. [34] and expressed in Equations 3 and 4. This viscoplastic model is incorporated within the constitutive law for the polymer subcells (Equation 5).

$$d\varepsilon_i^f = S_{ij}^f d\sigma_j^f \quad i, j = 1 \cdots 6 \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^f = 2D_0 \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{Z}{\sigma_e} \right)^{2n} \right] \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}^{dev}}{2\sqrt{J_2}} + \alpha \delta_{ij} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_e = \sqrt{3J_2} + \sqrt{3}\alpha\sigma_{kk} \quad (4)$$

$$d\varepsilon_i^m = S_{ij}^m d\sigma_j^m + d\varepsilon_i^f \quad i, j = 1 \cdots 6 \quad (5)$$

In Equation 2, the variables $d\varepsilon^f$ and $d\sigma^f$ represent the strain and stress increments of the fiber subcells, respectively, and S^f contains the components of the compliance matrix for the fiber subcells. In Equations 3 and 4, Z and α are variables related to the resistance of molecular flow and hydrostatic stress effects, respectively, D_0 is the maximum inelastic strain rate, and the variable n controls the rate dependence of the material. σ^{dev} contains the deviatoric stress components, J_2 is the second invariant of the deviatoric stress tensor, and σ_{kk} is the summation of normal stress components. The variables $d\varepsilon^m$ and $d\sigma^m$ represent the strain and stress increments of the polymer matrix subcells, respectively, and S^m contains the components of the compliance matrix for the polymer matrix subcells. $d\varepsilon^f$ is the inelastic strain increment of the polymer matrix subcells, which is obtained through explicit solutions. The interphase subcells use a transversely isotropic, linear elastic model and the constitutive equations are similar to that of the fiber subcells described in Equation 2. For the comparison studies with different interphase properties from the literature, the constitutive law is linear elastic with either isotropic or transversely isotropic material orientations based on the assumptions outlined in the respective studies.

The current model accounts for damage and failure through several criteria which are applied at both the subcell and unit cell levels. The progressive damage model is based on a work potential theory [35], which is thermodynamics based and is able to capture microscale damage by discretizing the strain energy into elastic and damage components. This work potential theory has been employed in a plane stress damage model developed by Pineda et al. [36] and Pineda [37] where they integrated the progressive damage model with a generalized method of cells approach. A 3D incremental derivation of this progressive damage theory has also been applied to a 3D sectional micromechanical model [19, 20] by the authors; it is this version that is applied to the microscale subcells in the current modeling framework. The microscale failure modes of the polymer and interphase subcells in this work are determined through a maximum strain criterion and maximum stress criterion, respectively. The maximum strain criterion for the polymer subcells is defined based on the highly nonlinear response caused by the viscoplastic behavior of the polymer. There are six possible microfailure modes for the interphase and polymer subcells based on the assigned criteria, and the corresponding stress component is set to zero when the criteria for that specific mode is exceeded. The macroscale failure criteria of the unit cell are based on a modified Hashin failure theory that incorporates the shear stress effect in the compressive fiber failure mode, not considered in the original Hashin failure theory [38, 39].

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The nanoscale properties of the interphase were obtained through simulated testing of the atomistic interphase unit cell. Deformation was applied to the polymer matrix with a constant velocity of 0.001 Å/fs, and the carbon atom chains in the pseudo-damaged region of the graphene layers were stretched as the polymer matrix was deformed. The breakage of the chains was observed at approximately 5% strain. Figure 6 demonstrates the initial and final deformation of the atoms from a tensile test simulated by pulling the polymer matrix atoms in the interphase. Figure 7 shows a stress-strain plot obtained from this tensile test where the stress values were calculated from the Lagrangian virial stress definition of the molecular system [40]. From the plot, various dynamic behaviors of the system can be observed: elastic behavior, yield strength, and softening. Since the stress values from the MD simulation have large fluctuations due to atomic vibrations (red solid line), a moving average filter was applied for data

regression (blue dotted line). From the regressed data, the calculated transverse elastic modulus is 39.89 GPa.

Figure 6: Equilibrated nanoscale model before the virtual tensile test (left) and after the virtual tensile test (right).

Figure 7: Transverse tensile response of the nanoscale interphase model.

The properties determined from the nanoscale MD simulation of the interphase were incorporated into the interphase subcells defined in the HFGMC micromechanics approach. Various interphase properties from the literature were investigated at the microscale to compare with the aforementioned MD simulated properties. Table 2 displays the properties for each interphase type, including the current MD simulated properties, as well as several of the transverse elastic properties for the fiber and epoxy. Type 1 interphase refers to a rule of mixtures approximation of the interphase with a 50% fiber volume fraction and a 50% polymer volume fraction. The assumption for this interphase type is that the carbon fiber surface is pristine. Type 2 interphase applies the properties obtained from the work performed by Wang et al. [10] where they calculated the properties using dynamic modulus imaging methods. Type 3 interphase applies properties obtained from Zhang et al. [11] using a cohesive law derived from the Lennard-Jones potential. Since the nanoscale models cannot capture microscale defects, Zhang applied a defect factor of approximately 10% to reduce the tensile strength. Type 4 interphase properties are defined by Asp et al. [7], and the current interphase model properties consist of the results calculated from the MD simulations in this study. Due to the complexity of the molecular structure of the interphase in the current model, it is difficult to ascertain if the volume fractions in this interphase type are similar to the values of the Type 1 interphase. However, the ratio of the number of atoms in the carbon fiber surface to the number of atoms in the polymer matrix can be extracted from the MD simulations and this

ratio was approximately 50:50. While the nanoscale interphase model simulates complex fiber/matrix interaction and nanoscale defects, it does not take into account larger microscale defects due to the small size of the nanoscale model and the large computational costs associated with increasing the size of the model. Thus, a 10% defect factor was also applied to the transverse tensile strength simulated by MD.

	Transverse Modulus (GPa)	Poisson Ratio	Transverse Tensile Strength (MPa)
Carbon Fiber	13.8	0.25	
Epoxy	3.52	0.4	
Interphase:			
Type 1	6.43	0.33	50
Type 2 [10]	12.7	0.35	50
Type 3 [11]	3.37	0.4	53
Type 4 [7]	34	0.2	
Current Model	39.9	0.35	171

Table 2: Constituent material properties.

The transverse tensile modeling results were obtained by applying a strain rate of 1.05 s^{-1} to the PMC microscale unit cell. The arrow dissecting the unit cell in Figure 5 indicates where the subcell stress values were extracted in order to plot the transverse tensile stress as a function of distance through the width of the unit cell. The results for each interphase type are shown in Figure 8(a). These results illustrate the effect of different interphase properties on the stress gradient across the unit cell and, specifically, across the interfacial fiber/matrix boundary. In order to better view this stress gradient for each interphase type, the damage and failure criteria are not applied. For the current MD simulated interphase type, the stress gradient across the interphase is shown to be larger than that of the other interphase types due to the strong physical interaction between fiber and polymer matrix, which results in a large elastic modulus for the interphase. The unit cell response for each interphase type is depicted in Figure 8(b) and includes the microdamage theory, microfailure criteria, and macrofailure criteria. The unit cell response for the current MD simulated interphase model shows that the predicted composite tensile strength of this particular interphase type is approximately 7% less than the other interphase types and also exhibits a maximum difference of 10% in failure strain.

Figure 8: Transverse tensile modeling results using different interphase types showing a) the stress as a function of distance through the width of the unit cell and b) the unit cell stress-strain response.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

A multiscale framework was developed to integrate the nanoscale interphase model with a HFGMC micromechanics theory. For the nanoscale interphase model, pseudo-damaged graphene layers and a thermoset polymer matrix were combined to represent the physical molecular structure of the carbon fiber/polymer matrix interphase. While there is a large variation in the literature on interphase properties, the MD simulated modulus of the nanoscale interphase was similar to several values found in the literature. In addition, the microscale model includes interphase subcells, with properties defined by the nanoscale interphase model, and shows that the strong fiber/polymer interaction at the nanoscale corresponded to a high stress gradient in the interphase region at the microscale. For comparison, the interphase properties extracted from the literature were incorporated within the current modeling framework. The results showed that the unit cell response, with the MD simulated interphase properties, predicted a composite tensile strength that was approximately 7% lower than the other interphase types and also predicted a maximum difference of 10% in failure strain. Future studies will include extension of the interphase model to account for different possible orientations of the graphene layers as well as different types of defect geometries. Additional work will be performed at the microscale to assign stochastic interphase properties around the circumference of the carbon fiber, which will better represent the physical, amorphous structure of the fiber and interphase.

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